

Terpenoids: Part XXVII. Synthesis of di- β -Sesquiphellandrene

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Through the application of Wittig reaction, a synthesis of di- β -sesquiphellandrene, isomeric with zingiberene has been accomplished.

(-) β -Sesquiphellandrene, a monocyclic sesquiterpene hydrocarbon, has been recently isolated¹ in a pure form by Sutherland *et al* from the ginger oil. The constitution (I) has been assigned on the basis of chemical properties and physical evidences. The stereochemistry of the naturally occurring hydrocarbon has been worked out and found to be identical with that of (-) zingiberene(II).

Earlier Eschenmoser and Schinz² suggested tentatively the presence of β -phellandrene-like sesquiterpene along with the naturally occurring zingiberene on the basis of ultra-violet absorption spectrum. Also in the various synthesis of zingiberene reported in literature³⁻⁵, in which tertiary carbinol(III) was employed as an intermediate, β -sesquiphellandrene was formed as one of the undesired dehydration product and thus always accompanied the final product zingiberene, but no formal synthesis of this hydrocarbon has been reported so far. In the present studies* we report an unambiguous synthesis of di- β -sesquiphellandrene.

The sequence of reactions employed for this purpose is depicted below:

1. D. W. Connel and M. D. Sutherland, *Australian J. Chem.*, 1966, **19**, 283.
2. A. Eschenmoser, and H. Schinz. *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1950, **33**, 171.
3. S. M. Mukherji and N. K. Bhattacharyya, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 4698.
4. R. C. Banerjee, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, **21**, 285.
5. G. D. Joshi and S. N. Kulkarni, *Indian, J. Chem.*, 1965, **3**, 91.

*A part of this work was read at Aligarh during C.S.I.R. Convention; December (1965).

2,6-Dimethyl-8 (N-pyrrolidyl)-2, 7-octadiene (IV) was obtained from dl-citronellal according to the method of Stork *et al*⁶ for enamine formation. The compound (IV) showed characteristic I.R. peaks at 1650 (enamine) 830, 785 (trily substituted double bond), 1370 and 1460 cm^{-1} (C-CH₃).

The enamine (IV) on treatment with methyl vinyl ketone under nitrogen atmosphere and subsequent refluxing with acetic acid furnished 6-(4-keto- Δ^2 -cyclohexenyl)-2-methyl- Δ^2 -heptene (V). The unsaturated ketone (V) was characterised through its 2:4-dinitrophenyl-hydrazone derivative. The I.R. spectrum of the unsaturated ketone showed peaks at 1695 (C=O), 1618 (conju). The U. V. spectrum showed maximum at $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 227 $\text{m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon=3.66$). Lit.⁷ reports $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 225 $\text{m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon=3.76$).

Wittig reaction⁸ with methyl triphenyl phosphonium iodide to (V) in the presence of methyl sulphanyl carbanion under nitrogen, afforded the hydrocarbon (VI) in 76.9% yield. The synthetic hydrocarbon (VI) was characterised through peaks at 1637, 1598, 885 (terminal methylene). The lit.¹ reports peaks at 1634, 876 (terminal methylene). It absorbs at $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 232 $\text{m}\mu$ ($\log \epsilon=3.562$). Lit.¹ reports $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 232 $\text{m}\mu$ (ϵ 19300).

EXPERIMENTAL

M. p. s and b.p.s. are uncorrected. Microanalysis by Drs. Weiller and Strauss, Oxford. I.R. absorption spectra were recorded on Beckman I-R.-5 with sodium chloride optics and using a thin liquid film.

2, 6-Dimethyl-8 (N-pyrrolidyl)-2, 7-octadiene (IV).—The enamine (II) was prepared from dl-citronellal and pyrrolidine according to the method of Stork *et al*.

6-(4-Keto- Δ^2 -cyclohexenyl)-2-methyl- Δ^2 -heptene(V).—To the enamine (IV) (14 g. 0.067 mole) was added under nitrogen with stirring, methyl vinyl ketone (4.69; 0.067 mole) over a period of 45 min. at 0°. After standing for 48 hr. at room temperature, the contents were heated with acetic acid (50 ml.) (4 hr.). Most of the acetic acid was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was taken in ether and the rest of the acetic acid was removed by washing the ethereal extract with water. After drying, the solvent was evaporated and the residue on vacuum distillation gave the ketone (V), 6g. (42.8 %), b.p. 160°/6 mm. (Found: C, 82.29; H, 9.77; C₁₄H₂₂O requires C, 82.3; H, 9.87%).

The ketone gave the red 2:4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone (methyl alcohol) which melted at 119°. Lit.⁷ m.p. 118°. (Found: N, 14.48; C₂₀H₂₈N₄ requires N, 14.5%).

dl- β -Sesquiphellandrene(VI): A solution of sodium sulfinyl carbanion was prepared under nitrogen from sodium hydride (0.28 g.) and dimethyl sulphoxide (5.5 ml.). The solution was cooled in cold water and stirred during the addition of methyltriphenyl

6. G. Stork, Brizzolaro and R. Terrel, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 207.

7. Gita Mukherji, B. K. Ganguly, R. C. Banerji and J. C. Bardhan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 2402,

8. Greenwald, Chaykovsky and Corey, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1963, **28**, 1128,

phosphonium iodide (2.4 g.) in dimethyl sulphoxide (11.5 ml.) whereupon the reddish colour of methylenephosphorane was obtained. After stirring at room temperature for 15 min., the ketone (V) (1.04 g.) in tetrahydrofuran (5 ml.) was added and stirring continued for 3 hr. at 60°. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into cold water. The organic layer was taken up in petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) and washed thrice with cold water. After removal of the solvent, the compound (VI) was purified by passing through alumina (elution with petroleum) which on further distillation under reduced pressure gave (VI), (0.8 g.) in 76.9% yield, b.p. 128-129°/7 mm. η^{27}_D 1.4978. Lit.¹ η^{25}_D 1.4973. (Found: C, 88.01; H, 11.99; C₁₅H₂₄ requires C, 88.16; H, 11.84%).

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